

EXPLORING LIBRARIANS' KNOWLEDGE, TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE, AND UTILIZATION OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

Emerging technologies have infiltrated libraries globally, which has caused libraries in higher education institutions to improve and align their operations and services with recent technological innovations. As a result, library services can now be delivered online, collections are digitized, and technological tools are being utilized to monitor resources and analyze data. This study aims to explore librarians' knowledge and technology acceptance and determine its influence on their utilization of emerging technologies. This study used the descriptive-correlational research design and analyzed the gathered data using descriptive and inferential statistics. The participants were fifty (50) academic librarians employed in Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao who utilized emerging technologies. Online survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the participants. Findings reveal that librarians' knowledge of emerging technologies considering artificial intelligence (AI) was generally high, and moderate for big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things. The librarians' level of technology acceptance in terms of perceived ease of use and usefulness was generally high, and their utilization of artificial intelligence, big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things was also generally high. Moreover, the librarians' knowledge and level of technology acceptance significantly influenced their utilization of emerging technologies. It was noted that participants' level of technology acceptance came out to have significantly influenced their utilization of emerging technologies. The study confirms that librarians' knowledge and technology acceptance are crucial in today's digital age for them to keep abreast with the changes.

Keywords: *librarians, knowledge, technology acceptance, emerging technologies*

INTRODUCTION

New technologies have constantly emerged from numerous fields of modern society. These technologies have brought unprecedented changes on how people live, work, and interact with the world. Due to the increasing trends and demands of economic globalization, the life cycle of technology innovation has grown relatively fast, thus affecting existing industries (Yang & Li, 2016).

Accordingly, there have been restructuring and expansions in Information Technology (IT) and related fields which paved the way to a new breed of technologies called emerging technologies. Rotolo and Martin (2015) defined emerging technologies as "*novel technologies that show a consistent presence over time and have the potential to influence socio-economic domains significantly. Nevertheless, its primary influence is anticipated in the future, making the initial emergence phase somewhat uncertain and ambiguous.*" Yang and Li (2016) mentioned that emerging technologies are technological tools being developed and will substantially have a significant impact on the corporate, social environment, and modern information society. It gives thorough emphasis on Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, Cloud Computing, and Internet of Things (IoT), to mention a few.

These technologies have since infiltrated the workplace globally including libraries. With this, libraries have had to adapt and reinvent in order to be relevant at a time when knowledge is easily accessible and digitalization has transformed how people exchange, consume, and preserve knowledge. Igwe and Sulyman (2022) ascertain that this innovation provides opportunities to a new breed of libraries to improve information access, dissemination, and delivery of services. Eje and Dushu (2018) further argue that libraries can revolutionize service delivery and information access by making use of developing technologies, such as digitalization and online databases, to provide access to a wide range of materials without time and geographical restrictions.

Emerging technologies also offer promising opportunities for libraries in developing countries, such as the Philippines, to modernize and automate their operations, streamline library services, and better serve the communities. That being said, libraries in the Philippines are implementing digital cataloging and management systems to improve access to information resources, particularly in remote and underprivileged areas. It also aids in preserving cultural heritage by digitizing rare manuscripts and historical documents, thereby enhancing literacy, education, and research in the country.

In view of the foregoing, Wenborn (2018) suggests that in light of recent technological advancements, libraries and librarians have had to be flexible and adaptable to meet the requirements of their patrons in terms of research and learning. Librarians, therefore, must have adequate knowledge and readiness for technology integration to tackle globalization challenges. Nevertheless, amidst these technological innovations and its integration in libraries, librarians still suffer from issues in integrating new technologies (Wheatley, 2018). The vast numbers of emerging technologies are not properly

introduced to library and information professionals. For this reason, libraries and librarians integrate new technologies without receiving strategic training and knowledge despite the fact that these technologies have redefined and changed their duties (Carson & Little, 2014; Cherinet, 2018; Dowdy, 2020a; Ratledge & Sproles, 2017; Tritt & Kendrick, 2014). Among the challenges that librarians face in integrating new technologies is the fact that there is a knowledge and skills gap (Adjei, 2023). With limited knowledge and skills, librarians may not be able to understand the complexities in operating and navigating the technologies while using them in their workplace. As a result, librarians may not be able to fully adopt, effectively utilize, and maximize the potential benefits of emerging technologies in their service delivery and accomplishment of tasks.

There is also a pressing significant gap in the Philippine context on studies about emerging technologies. To date, studies conducted in the Philippines are limited only on the advantages and librarians' perceptions of integrating emerging technologies in libraries and other industries, and they do not focus on librarians' knowledge, acceptance, and utilization of such technologies. This entails that librarians' knowledge about emerging technologies has not been studied comprehensively. Further, its influence on their technology adoption and utilization has not been looked into. Hence, this study embarked into the exploration of the knowledge and acceptance of emerging technologies among librarians in Caraga and Northern Mindanao Region, as well as how they have utilized these technologies in their libraries to fully understand how awareness and knowledge of the practical application of emerging technologies influence their adoption and extent of utilization.

Research Questions

This study determined the extent of knowledge, acceptance, and utilization of emerging technologies among academic librarians in the Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao. Specifically, it explored to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' assessment of their knowledge of emerging technologies considering the following:
 - 1.1. artificial intelligence;
 - 1.2. big data;
 - 1.3. cloud computing; and
 - 1.4. internet of things?
2. What is the level of technology acceptance in terms of:
 - 2.1. perceived ease of use; and
 - 2.2. perceived usefulness?
3. What is the extent of the participants' utilization of emerging technologies considering the following:
 - 3.1. artificial intelligence;
 - 3.2. big data;
 - 3.3. cloud computing; and
 - 3.4. internet of things?

4. Do the participants' knowledge and technology acceptance significantly influence their utilization of emerging technologies?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the different higher education institutions in Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao whose librarians are utilizing emerging technologies in their workplace for service delivery and accomplishment of tasks.

Participants of the Study and Sampling Procedures

This study focused on the current state of knowledge of emerging technologies among academic librarians in the Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao. In selecting the participants for this study, the researcher conducted an inquiry to identify librarians from Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao who adopt and utilize emerging technologies in their libraries. It involved communicating with librarians to gain information about emerging technologies adopted in their libraries and their engagement with such technologies. Specifically, this study exclusively included librarians who have adopted and utilized emerging technologies. Thus, employing a total enumeration of librarians who utilize emerging technologies, all fifty (50) librarians from different higher education institutions in the Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao were selected as the participants and responded to the survey.

This study excluded librarians who were not utilizing emerging technologies to maintain the validity and reliability of the research findings and ensure that the data collected from the participants directly addresses the research objectives.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a modified questionnaire based from the study of Warkentin et al. (2007) and incorporated items from various print and electronic sources (Casey, 2022; Pew Research Center, 2024; Chhetri, 2023; Evans & Wood, 2018; Barman, 2023; De Sarkar, 2023; Bolasco, 2023; Ball, 2019; Hussain & Ahmad, 2021; Sashidhara, 2023). The research instrument was composed of three parts. The first part of the research instrument was composed of forty questions to test and assess librarians' knowledge of emerging technologies in terms of: Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Cloud Computing, and Internet of Things. The second part consists of twelve items for librarians' level of technology acceptance based on perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The third part of the research instrument consists of sixteen items for librarians' utilization of emerging technologies.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The study employed descriptive statistics to answer Problems 1, 2, and 3. Descriptive statistics such as weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the participants' assessment of their knowledge, level of technology acceptance, and

utilization of emerging technologies. For Problem 4, regression analysis was used to determine if there is a significant influence of the participants' knowledge and level of technology acceptance on their utilization of emerging technologies.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on the current state of knowledge of emerging technologies among academic librarians in the Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao. The emerging technologies encompass Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, knowledge and acceptance of emerging technologies in terms of perceived ease of use and usefulness. It also explored librarians' utilization of emerging technologies in different library practices. Nonetheless, the research instruments were floated out from February to April 2024. The study utilized surveys to gather data from the participants. The research instrument used in the study consisted of test questions on the concepts of emerging technologies, and items for technology acceptance and utilization of emerging technologies. This research excluded the librarians who did not adopt and utilize emerging technologies; hence, this research aimed to provide insights into the technology acceptance and utilization among academic librarians in the Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao and hope to shed light on potential areas for improvement in their digital competencies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the summary of the participant's assessment of their knowledge of emerging technologies. As shown in the table below, librarians' knowledge of emerging technologies, considering artificial intelligence, obtained a higher rating than other emerging technologies, indicated by the overall mean of 7.28. This implies that of the four (4) emerging technologies considered in this study, the participants thoroughly understand only the concepts and application of artificial intelligence in libraries. This can be attributed to some training and workshops conducted by associations such as the Philippine Librarians' Association to orient librarians about the benefits and advantages of using AI in libraries. Similarly, a study by Andersdotter (2023) emphasized the increase in librarians' level of knowledge about artificial intelligence through training courses that discuss concepts and contents on AI from a library perspective.

Table 1. Summary of Participants' Knowledge of Emerging Technologies

Knowledge of Emerging Technologies	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Artificial Intelligence	7.28	High	1.64
Big Data	6.56	Average	2.11
Cloud Computing	6.28	Average	1.92
Internet of Things	5.84	Average	2.34
Overall	6.49	Average	2.00

Legend: Very High = 9.0 - 10 High = 7.0 - 8.99 Moderate = 5.0 - 6.99 Low = 3.0 - 4.99 Very Low = 1.0 - 2.99

Table 2 summarizes the participants' level of technology acceptance in terms of perceived ease of use and usefulness. Among the two factors, perceived usefulness was "very high," indicated by the mean of 4.51. This implies that librarians are more likely to utilize technology when it could enhance their job performance. Similarly, studies emphasized that the perceived usefulness of a tool is a factor that influences technology adoption the most. Therefore, it has to be considered the most (Davis, 1989; Scherer, Siddiq & Tondeur, 2019).

In general, the level of technology acceptance obtained an overall mean of 4.33, which indicates "high" technology acceptance among the participants. This means that the ease of using technologies and their usefulness in their job are being considered by librarians when adopting a new technology in their workplace.

Table 2. Summary of Participants' Level of Technology Acceptance

Technology Acceptance	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Perceived Ease of Use	4.16	High	0.55
Perceived Usefulness	4.51	Very High	0.48
Overall	4.33	High	0.51

Legend: Very High = 4.51 - 5 High = 3.51 - 4.50 Average = 2.51 - 3.50 Low = 1.51 - 2.50 Very Low = 1.0 - 1.50

Table 3 presents the summary of the participants' utilization of emerging technologies. Among the four (4) emerging technologies considered in this study, it is cloud computing which obtained the highest mean, indicated by the mean 4.31. This implies that librarians are aware of the many applications of cloud computing in libraries and they are utilizing it to store and share resources online, and host digital libraries, thereby providing access to remote users. This could be attributed to the capability of cloud computing to provide storage, thus allowing users to store large amounts of e-books and files online (Eversoll, 2023).

Furthermore, among the four (4) emerging technologies, it is Artificial Intelligence which obtained the lowest rating in terms of utilization, indicated by a mean of 3.92. This implies that librarians Artificial Intelligence is utilized in libraries to a lesser extent than other emerging technologies. This could be attributed to how librarians perceived AI regarding their relevance in library services. Similarly, a study reported that librarians are concerned about adopting AI in libraries since it may replace human intelligence once it is integrated in library services (Subaveerapandiyar & Gozali, 2024).

The overall mean of 4.18 for the participants' utilization of emerging technologies also implies that these technologies are highly utilized by librarians for a number of reasons such as to deliver their services efficiently, automate their processes, manage collections, and enhance user experience (Ukamaka & Kakiri, 2021; Sun et al., 2018; Hamad et al., 2020).

Table 3. Summary of Participants' Utilization of Emerging Technologies

Emerging Technologies	Overall Mean	Interpretation	SD
Artificial Intelligence	3.92	High	0.74
Big Data	4.24	High	0.73
Cloud Computing	4.31	High	0.67
Internet of Things	4.28	High	0.79
Overall	4.18	High	0.73

Legend: Very High = 4.51 – 5.00 High = 3.51 - 4.50 Average = 2.51 - 3.50 Low = 1.51 - 2.50 Very Low = 1.0 - 1.50

Table 4 shows the regression analysis of the influence of participants' knowledge and technology acceptance on their utilization of emerging technologies. Findings reveal that the whole model is significant ($F=58.76$, $p = .000$). Participants who have higher knowledge about technologies and have higher technology acceptance tend to have higher utilization of emerging technologies. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The findings suggest that librarians' adoption and utilization of emerging technologies are influenced by their familiarity with the technology and their usefulness and proficiency in using the technology. This entails that librarians highly utilize technologies that they find easy to operate and is useful in their job.

Furthermore, 71.4 percent of the variability in their utilization of emerging technologies can be accounted for by a combination of their knowledge and technology acceptance levels ($R^2=.714$). This indicates a strong predictive relationship between the factors knowledge and technology acceptance, and utilization of emerging technologies. This implies that high knowledge and high technology acceptance explains high utilization of emerging technologies. This confirms various claims that knowledge and technology acceptance significantly influence librarians' adoption of emerging technologies (Gholami et al., 2018; Otubelu & Anunobi, 2020). The other 28.6 percent may be attributed to other factors not covered in this study such as management support, availability of resources like budget and IT personnel, and infrastructure readiness.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants' Knowledge and Technology Acceptance on their Utilization of Emerging Technologies

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.557	.467		-1.19	.239
Knowledge	-.032	.032	-.079	-.987	.329
Technology Acceptance	1.14	.106	.857	10.77**	.000
Model Summary					
R = .845	R ² = .714	Adjusted R ² = .702	F = 58.76**	p = .000	

**significant at 0.01 level

Conclusions

Librarians' knowledge about emerging technologies is relevant in today's library setting. The librarians who participated in this study possess knowledge about emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things. They utilize emerging technologies in providing services to their users, managing their resources, and performing their duties. Evidently, their knowledge of emerging technologies plays a pivotal role as it significantly influences their adoption and utilization of these emerging technologies. Thus, it is necessary for librarians to continuously update their knowledge about technologies to stay competent with the use of the technologies that are present and adopted in their workplace.

Librarians with high technology acceptance integrate and utilize emerging technologies in their libraries. The findings of this study validate the previous claims that the level of technology acceptance significantly influences a user's intention to adopt and utilize technology by Gholami et al. (2018), Adeleke (2019), Otubelu & Anunobi (2020), and Aiyebelehin & Omekwu (2020). Further, this confirms Davis' Technology Acceptance Model (1989) which theorized that users adopt and accept a technology when they perceive it easy to use and is useful in their job. Librarians may also need to acquire training and educate themselves by reading about technologies to be updated with the recent technological trends relevant to libraries as this could be helpful in understanding the essential functions and roles of technologies in the workplace. It is also crucial for librarians to be knowledgeable about emerging technologies for them to keep abreast with the changes in providing more effective, innovative, and efficient services in the library. Thus, possessing knowledge about how to operate and implement a technology maximizes its potential of assisting librarians in their work.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher endorses the following recommendations:

1. That Library associations may provide more seminars and training on emerging technologies, focusing on their concepts and practical applications to libraries.
2. That Library administrators may support their librarians in enhancing their knowledge about emerging technologies by allocating financial resources intended for seminars and training; the results may also encourage library administrators to develop an ICT plan highlighting the importance of acquiring technologies in achieving the library's goal of supporting the teaching, learning, and research needs of its community.
3. That Librarians may:
 - 3.1. seek to continue acquiring more knowledge about emerging technologies specifically about Big Data, Cloud Computing; and Internet of Things;
 - 3.2. consider conducting orientation programs to acquaint faculty with these technologies, as they may also utilize some of them in their work; and

- 3.3. implement strategies and policies on the responsible use of AI in their libraries.
 4. That Schools offering library and information science may consider reviewing and updating their curriculum to include courses on emerging technologies that are part of the industry needs.
 5. That Future researchers may explore librarians' knowledge and utilization of other emerging technologies such as augmented and virtual reality.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher sought the approval of the school's Research Ethics Committee to ensure that the ethical standards and scientific merit of this study are being considered as it involved the participation of human subjects. After the approval of the above-mentioned committee, the researcher requested through writing for the list and total number of academic librarians in Caraga Region from the President and Officers of the Philippine Librarians Association - Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao Librarians Council. The letter was sent to the email addresses of the council officers. After granting the request, another letter was written and sent to ask permission from the presidents and/or campus directors, and library heads in Caraga Region and Northern Mindanao to permit the researcher to conduct her study. Upon approval, the researcher sent a letter to the participants informing them that they were identified as participants of the study. After which, the researcher sent a separate consent form which was completed by the participants. The participants indicated their consent by affirming the consent form. The researcher collected the consent form and determined whether the participants agreed to participate in the study. After identifying who among the participants gave their consent, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to the identified participants by sending the Google Form link to their e-mail addresses and Facebook accounts. The purpose of the study was indicated in the Google form survey questionnaire and a set of instructions were also included for the participants to be clarified before answering the questionnaire. They were given two (2) hours to answer. After answering the questions, the accomplished questionnaires were retrieved from the participants and tallied to generate the findings of this study.

The participants were assured that all their responses were treated with utmost confidentiality and all information received from them were acknowledged and accurately presented. Furthermore, to avoid possible conflict of interest, librarians who were identified as participants in this study but were under the leadership of the researcher in their respective workplaces were excluded from participation.

Moreover, the researcher was responsible for collecting, handling, and safeguarding the information and responses from the participants. She was the only person who could access the personal information and the data collected from the participants, thus maintaining the privacy and security of their information. Thus, the researcher ensured that their responses were treated with utmost confidentiality. The form did not require the

participants to write their names; instead, they were identified by a unique number. Only the researcher had access to the survey results and if, in any case, other individuals requested the participants' personal information and responses, the researcher would establish a data-sharing agreement.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

Their participation in this research was entirely voluntary, and they could withdraw at any stage without facing any consequences. If, for any reason, the participants experienced discomfort, dissatisfaction, or distress and they decided to discontinue, they could contact the researcher through phone, e-mail, or Facebook regarding their decision to withdraw. The researcher would respect their decision, and it would not affect, in any way, their relationship with the researcher or any affiliated organizations. If, in any case, the participants had shared personal information with the researcher, they still had the right to request the shared information to be withheld and not to be included in the study. The researcher would maintain confidentiality of information in case of withdrawals from participants.

Risks

This study involved test questions to test and assess librarians' knowledge of emerging technologies. If, at any point, the participants found a question too personal or thought that answering specific questions made them uncomfortable, they had the option to skip the question or discontinue their participation. Other than this, this study involved no known risks.

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